

**STUDY ON DIVERSITY OF TERRESTRIAL INSECTS IN
KARIMUDDANAHALLY, MYSORE DISTRICT OF KARNATAKA****Dr. SUCHITRA GURUSHANKAR**Department of Zoology,
Maharani's Science College for Women,
Mysore - 570 005, Karnataka, India**Dr. SHEREEN KOUSER***Department of Zoology,
Yuvaraja's College (autonomous), University of Mysore,
Mysore - 570005, Karnataka, India
Corresponding author: shereenkouser@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

A preliminary study of diversity of insects was done in Karimuddanahally village an agricultural site - Mysore district, Karnataka State. The survey carried out in a year May 2017 to July 2018. During the study period 48 species of insects belonging to 7 orders were found. The order Lepidoptera (25%) was dominant with 12 species followed by Coleoptera (16.67%), Hymenoptera (14.58%), Diptera (14.58%), Hemiptera (12.5%), Orthoptera (8.33%) and Odonata (8.33%). The fauna of insects study region was rich because of a variety of plantation, cropland, availability to access to food plants, ecological condition, temperature, humidity and rainfall.

Keywords

Insects, Lepidoptera, plantation, cropland.

INTRODUCTION

Insects are the largest group within the Arthropod phylum. Insects are the world's most diverse group of animals on the earth in terms of both taxonomic diversity and ecological functions. They have adopted for almost every conceivable type of environment from the equator to the arctic and from sea level to the snow field of the high mountains on land, in air, water and almost everywhere (Belamkar, and Jadesh, 2014). The class Insecta is a huge and high diversified group of animal kingdom with 1.5 million species representing near 90% of the animal kingdom (Mani, 1982). Four orders the Coleoptera, Diptera, Hymenoptera and Lepidoptera accounts for 81% of all the described species of living insects. The order Lepidoptera is one of the most species rich group of insects, with an estimated number of species close to 146,000 (Bakowski and Doku-Marfo, 2009). Insect biodiversity accounts for a large proportion of all biodiversity on the planet, over half of the estimated 1.5 million organism species described are classified as insects (Stork *et al.*, 2017). In terrestrial ecosystems insects function as herbivores, pollinators, seed dispersers, predators, parasites, detritivores or ecosystem engineers (Weisser and Seimann, 2008). Animals particularly insects are considered to pollinate nearly 70% of trees in lowland tropical rain forest (Bawa, 1990). Insects play a crucial role in ecosystem function. They cycle nutrients, pollinate plants, disperse seeds, maintain soil structure and fertility. Some insects are flightless, and hence vulnerable to environmental changes habitat fragmentation (Majer, 1987). India has 59,353 species of insects belonging to 619 families. Indian insects belong to 27 order of which Coleoptera is the most dominant with about 15,500 species. Butterflies and Moths with about 15,000 species is another important group. These are followed by Hymenoptera (10,000 spp.), Diptera (6093 spp.) and Hemiptera (6500 spp.) (Alfred *et al.*, 1998; Varshney, 1998). The richness of tropical insect fauna worldwide is beyond expectation, as insects are the significant components of animal diversity in terms of the number of species in most of the habitats and ecosystem (Stork, 1988). Nonetheless, only a few diversity studies consider insects (Yi *et al.*, 2011), although they are essential components in monitoring ecosystem (Lawton *et al.*, 1998; Losey *et al.*, 2006). Taxonomic identification of insects in diversity studies through parataxonomy and morphospecies is the need of the hour [Krell, 2004; Majka, 2006]. Taxonomic and biological studies have been conducted on the various

groups of insects found in the paddy field including pests and non-pests of rice, those preying on the rice crop and weed and their parasites predators (Yano, 1978). Butterflies are one of the most important assemblages of insects that act as biodiversity indicators as well as nature's gardeners. Owing to habitat destruction for developmental activities in urban environment and unscientific management of natural resources, much of our native butterflies are fast disappearing and at present, their survival is under threat (Nair *et al.*, 2014). The present study has been undertaken to conduct a survey on the diversity of terrestrial insects in Karimuddanahally village, Mysore district.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

Study site is an agricultural field in Karimuddanahally village, Hunsur Taluk, Mysore District, Karnataka State - located at a distance of 35 kms from Mysore in which the cropland was selected for observing the insect diversity. Vegetation type of cropland is paddy (grass) and common types of shrubs and some vegetarian crops were present. Study area has latitude of 12.20 27 ° N and longitude 76.3775°E.

Data Collection

Field work was conducted from May 2017 to July 2018. Species were observed by local visual method, and line transect method. Field survey was done with the fixed local path at an agricultural site to collect the data of the species and captured the photos at the agricultural site or local path of habitat. Field observations were made weekly 2 days for a month. Species were identified based on their wings, body shape, legs, structure habitat etc. To capture the insect photos and to identify the species Smartphone Redmi Note 10 was used

Diversity indices

Diversity indices were calculated by using the formulas as follows.

Margalef species richness DMg is $D = S - 1 / \ln N$, Where, S = Number of species and N = Number of individuals, Shannon diversity index $H_0 = - \sum p_i \ln p_i$, where p_i the proportional abundance of the i th species = n_i/N , Simpsons' index $H = \sum (N_i/N)^2$ where H is Simpson's index where N_i is the number of individuals for all S species and N is the known total number of individuals for all S species in population where calculated for study site (Mugurran, 2004).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 and 2 shows the Study Area. During the survey at an Agricultural site (study area), 48 species belonging to 29 families of 7 orders were recorded, of these individuals – order Lepidoptera were found to be dominant with 12 species followed by Coleoptera 8, Hymenoptera 7, Diptera 7, Hemiptera 6, Orthoptera 4 and Odonata 4 (Table 1). The order Lepidoptera spread over the families were recorded and also different species of butterflies including moths were recorded in Karimuddanahally, Mysore District, Karnataka.

In the present study, the highest number of observed insects species belonging to the order Lepidoptera (25%) similar observation made followed by Coleoptera (16.67%), Hymenoptera (14.58%), Diptera (14.58%), Hemiptera (12.5%), Orthoptera (8.33%) and Odonata (8.33%). The various environment factors such as temperature, humidity, rainfall, vegetation and food sources directly affecting the diversity and distribution of insect population. The diverse topography, vegetative features and climatic setting provided wide availability of food resting and breeding sites in a forest area (Uniyal and Mathur, 1998).

CONCLUSION

Among the 48 insects species were recorded in the study, the Lepidoptera species were dominant in terms of their density and occurrence. Higher value of Shannon – wiener index is attributed to higher number of species recorded at the site. The presence of large area with greater plant diversity provides diverse resources that contributed to insect diversity. Occurrence of maximum number of insects during summer is contributed to favorable condition but the human interference in the forms of upcoming construction results in lack of resting overall insect diversity.

IJETRM

International Journal of Engineering Technology Research & Management

(IJETRM)

<https://ijetrm.com/>

REFERENCE

1. Belamkar NV and Jadesh M. 2014. A preliminary study on abundance diversity of insect fauna in Gulbarga District, Karnataka, India, International journal of science and research, 3(12):1670-1675.
2. Mani MS. 1982. General Entomology: Oxford & IBH Publishing Company.
3. Bakowski M and Doku-Marfo E. 2009. A Rapid Biodiversity Assessment of the Ajenjua Bepo and Mamang River Forest Reserves, Eastern Region, Ghana. Conservation International, p.30-33.
4. Stork NE, McBroom J, Gely C and Hamilton AJ. 2017. New approaches narrow global species estimates for beetles, insects, and terrestrial arthropods. PNAS, 112 (24):7519-7523.
5. Weisser W and Seimann E. 2008. Ecological Studies: Insects and Ecosystem function.
6. Bawa KS. 1990. Plant pollinator interactions in tropical rain forests. Annual Review of Ecology and Systematics, 21:399-422.
7. Majer JD. 1987. The conservation and study of invertebrates in remnants of native vegetation, Nature Conservation: The Role of Remnants of Native Vegetation. Surrey Beatty & Sons, Sydney. p.333-335.
8. Alfred JRB, Das AK and Sanyal AK. 1998. Faunal diversity in India, Zoological Survey of India, Kolkata, p. 495. 1998.
9. Varshney RK. 1998. Faunal Diversity in India, Insecta, Zoological Survey of India, p. 146-157.
10. Stork NE. 1988. Insect diversity-facts, fiction and speculation. Biological Journal of Linnean Society, 35:321-37.
11. Yi Z, Jinchao F, Dayuan X, Weiguo S and Axmacher J. 2011. Insect diversity: Addressing an important but strongly neglected research topic in China. Journal of Resources and Ecology, 2:380-384.
12. Lawton JH, Bignell D, Bolton B and Bloemers GF. 1998. Biodiversity inventories, indicator taxa and effects of habitat modification in tropical forest. Nature, 391 (6662):72-76.
13. Losey JE and Vaughan M. 2006. The Economic Value of Ecological Services Provided by Insects. BioScience, 56:311-323.
14. Krell FT. 2004. Parataxonomy vs. taxonomy in biodiversity studies - Pitfalls and applicability of 'morphospecies' sorting. Biodiversity and Conservation 13(4):795-812.
15. Majka CG and Bondrup NS. 2006. Parataxonomy: A test case using beetles. Animal Biodiversity and Conservation, 29:149-156.
16. Yano K. 1978. Faunal and biological studies on the insects of paddy field in Asia, Part 1. Introduction and Sciomyzidae from Asia (Diptera). Esakia, 11:1-27.
17. Nair AV, Mitra P and Aditya S. 2014. Studies on the diversity and abundance of butterfly (Lepidoptera: Rhopalocera) fauna in and around Sarojini Naidu college campus, Kolkata, West Bengal, India. Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies, 2(4):129-134.
18. Mugurran AE. 2004. Measuring Biological Diversity, Blackwell Publishing, Oxford, p. 256.
19. Uniyal VP and Mathur PK. 1998. Diversity of butterflies in the great Himalayan National Park, Western Himalaya. Indian Journal of Forestry, 21(2):150-155.

Table 1 Order wise distribution of insect species observed from the study site

ORDER	FAMILY	COMMON NAME	SCIENTIFIC NAME	
LEPIDOPTERA	Nymphalidae	Angled castor	Aridnae merione	
		Common baron	Euthalia acounthea	
		Plain tiger	Danaus chrysippus	
	Papilionidae	Lime swallow tail	Papiliodemoleus	
		Common jay	Graphilumdoson	
		Common Mormon	Papilio polytes	
		Common rose	Pachiopta aristolochiae	
		Paeridae	Common grass yellow	Eurema hecabe
			Common vargrant	catopsilla florella
		Noctuidae	Brightowainscot	Oria musculosa
	Lycaenidea	Common pierrot	Catalicus rosimon	
		Tiny grass blue	zizula hylax	
	ODONATA	Coenagrionidae	Yellowaxtail	Ceriagrioncormande
Libbulidae		Common scarlet	Crocothemis erythraea	
		Ditch jewel	Branchythemis contaminate	
		Pailfaced clumbskimmer	Brachmorhogamendax	
DIPTERA	Clliphoridae	Common green bottlefly	Lucilia sericata	

IJETRM**International Journal of Engineering Technology Research & Management**

(IJETRM)

<https://ijetrm.com/>

		Common green blowfly	Lucilia cuprina
	Muscidae	House fly	Musca domestica
	Platypezidae	Paraplatypus	Paraplatypeza
	Stratimyidae	Soldier fly	Sargus
	Tachinidae	Tachinid flies	Winthemia
	Dolichopodidae	Long legged fly	Condylostylus
ORTHOPTERA	Acrididae	Band-winged grasshopper	Oedaleus infernalis
		Common field grasshopper	Caelifera
		Medow grasshopper	Pseudochorthippus parallelus
	Gryllidae	Black field grasshopper	Teleogryllus
COLEOPTERA	Crysomelidae	Bluemilkywedbeetle	Chrysochus cobaltinus
		White spotted flea beetle	Monolepta singnata
		Green tortoise beetle	Cassida circumdata

IJETRM**International Journal of Engineering Technology Research & Management**

(IJETRM)

<https://ijetrm.com/>

	Searabaeidae	Gapanees beetle	Popillia gaponicanewman
		Dung beetle	Scarabs
	Coccinelloidae	Lady bugs	Coccinellaseptempunctata
	Tenebridae	Dusty maize beetle	Gonocephalumsimplex
	Curculionidae	Amanananthus stemweevil	Hypolixus pica
HEMIPTERA	Blissidae	Chinch bugs	Blisscusleucopterus
	Coreidae	Box bug	Gonocerus
		Flat bug	Pentamorpha
	Dinidoridae	Red pumpkin bug	Coridivs janus
	Eurybrachidae	Planthopers	Eurybranchys
	Scutelleridae	Jewel bugs	Solenosthedium liligerum
HYMENOPTERA	Apidae	Asian honey bee	Apis cerana
		Rock honey bee	Apis dorsata
		Sulawesian honey bee	Apis nigrosincta
	Formicidae	Asian weaverant	Osmophilia smaragdina
		Rover ant	Brachymymex patagonicusmayr
	Megachilidae	Parasite bee	Stelis lateralis
	Vespidae	Red paper wasp	Ropalidia marginata

IJETRM

International Journal of Engineering Technology Research & Management
(IJETRM)

<https://ijetrm.com/>

Figure 1. Map of Karnataka showing Study Area

Figure 2. Study Area

IJETRM

International Journal of Engineering Technology Research & Management

(IJETRM)

<https://ijetrm.com/>

Figure 3. Order-wise distribution of insect species